

RESISTANCE THROUGH LITERATURE: AN ANALYSIS OF DALIT LITERATURE IN KERALA

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Abstract

The roots of Dalit literature in Kerala lies in the strong corpus of oral and ritualistic literature that interrogated the caste system and the practice of untouchability. Dalit literature began to be mainstreamed in India with the appearance of the English translations of Marathi Dalit writing. An Anthology of Dalit Literature, edited by Mulk Raj Anand and Eleanor Zelliot, and Poisoned Bread: Translations from Modern Marathi Dalit Literature, originally published in three volumes and later collected in a single volume, edited by Arjun Dangle [both published in 1992, the latter reissued recently in a new edition by Orient Black Swan], were perhaps the first books that popularised the genre throughout India. Not that there was no Dalit writing earlier: the origins of Dalit writing can be traced back to Buddhist literature; Dalit Bhakti poets like Gora, Raidas, Chokha Mela and Karma mela; and the Tamil Siddhas, or Chittar s (6th to 13th centuries C.E.), many of whom must have been Dalits going by hagiographical accounts like Periyapuram (12th century). But it was after the democratic and egalitarian thinkers such as Sree Narayana Guru, Jyotiba Phule, B.R. Ambedkar, Jyothi Thass, Sahodaran Ayyappan, Ayyankali, Poykayil Appachan and others cogently articulated the sources and modes of caste oppression that modern Dalit writing as a distinct genre began to emerge in Indian languages. The Dalit Panthers of Maharashtra (formed in 1972) and the writers like Baburao Bagul and Namdeo Dhasal who spearheaded the movement gave an impetus to Dalit writing in Marathi following Ambedkar's famous statement addressed to Gandhi, "Mahatma, I have no country." The rest of the story, from the publication of Dhasal's Golpitha (1972) onwards, is history. Now we have a significant corpus of Dalit literature in several of the Indian languages like Hindi, Marathi, Gujarati, Bengali, Odiya, Punjabi, Tamil, Telugu, Kannada and Malayalam, and representative works from these are getting translated into other languages, including English. Over the past one decade or so, more than five anthologies and quite a few autobiographies and works of fiction besides theoretical works and works by individuals, including Dhasal, have been published in English by various mainstream and alternative publishing houses in India. There are two volumes of writings from South India published recently: The Oxford India Anthology of Malayalam Dalit Writing, edited by M. Dasan, V. Pratibha, Pradeepan Pampirikunnu and C.S. Chandrika, and The Oxford India Anthology of Tamil Dalit Writing, edited by Ravikumar and R. Azhagar Asan (OUP, 2012), the first two volumes in a whole series of

similar anthologies under preparation. The editors of The Oxford India Anthology of Malayalam Dalit Writing have an important message for readers in their prefatory note: “Readers will discover the limitations of their reading practices as they encounter the emotional, intellectual and aesthetic demands of this collection and might feel uncomfortable at the challenge it poses as they realise their complicity with the status quo. These selections will also bring the mainstream critics and reviewers face to face with their own prejudices, who, insufficiently equipped to understand or accept the truth of Dalit experiences and perspectives, often label this body of writings ‘bitter’, ‘biased’, ‘militant’, ‘angry’, etc... and might, therefore, have missed its as not serious literary writing”.

Key Words: Caste System, Untouchability, Caste Oppression, Dalit Experience and perspectives

INTRODUCTION: -

Dalit literature has indeed created its own alternative aesthetic by redrawing the map of literature, by discovering and exploring a whole new continent of experience that had so far been left to darkness and silence, by helping literature overcome stagnation through a cleansing renewal, by disturbing the sterile complacency of the dominant social groups, and by challenging their set mores and fixed modes of looking at reality, their stale habits of ordering knowledge, beauty and power and their established literary canons, bringing to focus neglected, suppressed or marginalised aspects of experience, vision, language and reality and forcing the community to refashion its tools and observe itself critically from fresh and different angles. Dalit poetry, for example, challenges the assumptions and injunctions of classical poetics by breaking its rules of “propriety”, “balance”, “restraint” and “understatement”. Dalit literature also questions the middle-class notions of linguistic “decency” by using words that classical aesthetics would consider “uncouth” (chyutasamskara), “rustic” (gramya) or “obscene” (asleela). Both the anthologies carry exhaustive introductions that trace the origins of Dalit writing in the respective languages and put this non-canonical body of writing in its social, historical and cultural contexts and provide readers with a conceptual framework that is sure to help them appreciate the discourse better. They contain selections from both creative and critical genres and reveal the range of concerns, forms, styles and perspectives encompassed by the standardising term “Dalit writing” that often conceals its thematic and idiomatic diversity. The term “Dalit” began to be used in Kerala only in the 1970’s chiefly as the hegemonic discourse of the Kerala renaissance, despite its reformative zeal, succeeded in camouflaging the specificity of Dalit discourse and its difference from the dominant discourse of the time. It is to be noted here that the gaps and silences of the discourse of the Kerala renaissance began to be discovered and critiqued by subaltern intellectuals only in the last one decade or two when the famous “Kerala Model” of development also found its astute critics. Dalits and tribal people had been excluded from the idea of Malayali identity as even the

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historic Malayali Memorial, the mass petition submitted to the Maharaja of Travancore in 1891, did not demand jobs only for these sections. The class discourse too was used to render invisible the “cultural, symbolic and social capital” that their elite caste status had conferred on them. Many of the upper-caste reformers who pioneered the renaissance were progressive within their community but reactionary outside it. Their idea of emancipation was confined to their own respective communities. It was this context that forced Dalit organisations like the Sadhu Jana Paripalana Yogam to claim a distinct political space within the scenario of the emerging colonial modernity, leading to the struggles for the rights to education, hygiene, land and modern citizenship itself. Ayyankali, who wore clean clothes and a turban like the aristocrats and followed their physical postures, provided historical agency to the Dalits and turned the Dalit body into a site of resistance to feudal servitude and the Dalits’ labour and identity into negotiating signifiers. His anti-caste approach displeased the leaders of post- Independence parliamentary politics, but he would be the last to collaborate. Other movements followed, throwing up leaders like Poikayil Appachan, Pampadi John Joseph, K.P. Vallon and organisations, including the radical SEEDIAN (Socially, Educationally and Economically Depressed Indian Ancient Natives) of the 1970’s and the current DHRM (Dalit Human Rights Movement). The most important struggles in Kerala, like those in Muthanga and Chengara in the last decades, were led by Dalits and Adivasis who found that they had no seats in the international socialist feast and that the Marxist scheme of the class struggle might never fully grasp the complex cultural issues of anti- caste struggles. Need of Study: - In India’s unique social context, caste has acted as a source and mechanism of exclusion for certain groups of people resulting in disadvantage and deprivation. The perpetual deprivation of the people belonging to the lowest rung of the caste system for the past many centuries has acted as a powerful force in the construction of an identity of the deprived and oppressed. Now these people prefer to call themselves Dalits. In the contemporary context of Dalit identity and its articulations, the term Dalit signifies not simply a statistical category of the oppressed people but a collective. It represents a consciousness of the oppressed that seeks to create its own social and political space. Dalit identity and its cultural articulation are emerging as major themes in contemporary social science discourse.

Need of the study:-

Main aim of the study is focused on the development of Dalits and to ensure social equality among the mainstream society. The dominant viewpoint is that through these writing, they can convey their suppressed feelings to more people and hope for justice.

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Objectives of The Study: -

1. To generate an awareness of Dalits about their social situation in the society.
2. To understand the real cause of Dalit backwardness.
3. To find out the impact of Dalit literature on society.
4. To analyse the present scenario of Dalit life.

Methodology: -

The study is based on secondary data collected from reputed articles of research journals, books, website magazines etc. The study is all about to focus on Dalit literature of Kerala.

Emergence of Dalit Literature in Kerala: -

The roots of Dalit literature in Kerala as in Tamil Nadu lie in the strong corpus of oral and ritualistic literature that interrogated the caste system and the practice of untouchability and suggested an egalitarian spirituality and an organic humanism that encompassed the whole of creation. Both Poykayil Kumaragurudevan and Potheri Kunjambu, two of the pioneers of Dalit literature, reveal this tendency. The paradigm, however, undergoes a change in contemporary Dalit writers who share a modern literary sensibility and a great sensitivity towards language. Poets such as S. Joseph, M. B. Manoj, M. R. Renukumar, Vijila, Binu M. Pallippad and S. Kalesh and fiction writers such as T.K.C. Vaduthala, C. Ayyappan, Raghavan Atholi and P. A. Uthaman create a language of their own, often retrieving from oblivion words and phrases seldom used in mainstream Malayalam literature, though these stylistic nuances are difficult to capture in English. The anthology also carries examples of autobiographical writing by Kallen Pokkudan, an environmentalist, and critical interventions by thinkers such as K.K. Kochu, K.K. Baburaj, Kaviyoor Murali, Sanal Mohan, Sunny Kapikkad and Rekha Raj, among others. Tamil Dalit discourse follows a different trajectory. According to Ravikumar, who has written the introduction to the Tamil anthology, Vedic Brahminism gained ascendancy in Tamil Nadu only after the retreat of the relatively egalitarian Buddhist and Jain religions. Caste formation seems to have taken place sometime in the 12th and 13th centuries C.E. though it had been preceded by some form of social stratification. But the Brahmins were a minority and were prevented from entering Dalit residential areas; hence, the oppression they could inflict was rather minimal. It was with the formation of the South India Welfare Association in 1906 and the launch of the “Non-Brahmin Manifesto” in 1916 that Dalits began to face isolation and torture more than ever before as the non Brahmin space was entirely captured by high non-Brahmin castes, who were far larger in number than the Brahmins. Their

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Justice Party was clearly in favour of these castes, so much so that M.C. Rajah, a Dalit leader, had to lead a delegation to the Governor to complain about the injustices committed by the Justice Party on Dalits. The movements of certain backward castes like the Vanniyars only helped non-Dalits as some of these castes came to be designated as the Most Backward Castes (MBCs). The Dravida Munnetra Kazhagam and All India Anna Dravida Munnetra Kazhagam politics also gained from such movements. The implementation of the Mandal Commission report, too, benefited these sections, further marginalising Dalits. In the 1980's, small-scale Dalit movements began to emerge, producing in their wake a body of Dalit writing inspired to some extent by the African, Afro-American and Latin American literatures of resistance. However, they failed to link it up with the Buddhist past of the Tamil people. For the Marxists it was an expression of class oppression and for the followers of 'Periyar' E.V. Ramasamy, a new flowering of non-Brahmin literature. One can go beyond these stereotypes only if one understands thinkers like Lakshmi Narasu—who inspired Ambedkar—and Jyothi Thass, who read Tamil literature from a Buddhist point of view. This was a new kind of critique of Brahminism, different from the anti-Brahminism of the non-Brahmin leaders rooted in Hinduism. The best of writing in these anthologies is highly nuanced and uses invective, sarcasm and irony in articulating the Dalit dilemma. C. Ayyappan's Malayalam story, "Madness" (translator: Abhirami Sriram) is a good example. It is the monologue of a Dalit teacher, Krishnankutty, who refuses to accompany his sister when she is taken to the mental hospital or visit her in the asylum. In the course of the monologue, he explains to his friend why he had pretended not to see his sister when she was being thus taken by his neighbours and friends.

The following are some of the Malayalam Dalit writers and their works which are relevant in Dalit writings.

1. T.K.C Vaduthala (1921- 1988) (Original name Chathan T.K) Mainly known for short stories in the 1960s. Famous works- Chankaranthi Ada (1959, collection of stories), Achante Venthinga Inna (1957)
2. Thakazhi Sivasankara Pillai (1912-1999). Wrote about the marginalised and the working class. Examples:- His novels Thottiyude Makan (1947), Randidangazhi (1948)
3. Kumaran Asan (1873-1924) He was an Indian social reformer and Malayalam writer who was inspired by Buddhism. Works: Veena Poovu (1907), Duravastha (1922), Chandalabhikshuki (1922)

4. K. J Baby (1954-) He is a Dalit activist from Vayanadu. Famous works: Naatugaddika (play 1993), Mavelimantram (Novel 1991)
5. M. Mukundan (1942-) One of the modern Malayalam writers. His novel Pulayapaattu (2005) talked about adivasis of Kerala
6. P.A Uthaman, His novel Chavoli won Kerala Sahitya Academy award. It is set in the backdrop of Dalits.
7. Narayan (1940-), Known as the first tribal novelist of Kerala. He wrote about the Malayarayar community of Kerala. His novels Ooralikutti (1999) and Kocharathi (1998) are popular.
8. Kaviyoor Murali (1931-2001). He was a Dalit activist and Folklore researcher. His Dalit Bhasha Nighandu published in 1970 was a brilliant attempt to define Dalit language and its peculiarities.
9. C. Ayyappan (1949-2011), His short story collections “Njandukal” (DC Books, 2003), and “Uchamayakkathile swapnangal” (Sahitya Prasadhaka Cooperative Society, 1986), were considered as the turning points in the history of Malayalam Dalit writings. He uses the metaphors of madness and handedness in most of his stories to articulate the Dalit dilemma.
10. B. Jayamohan (1962-) Indian Tamil and Malayalam writer. His novel Nooru Simhasanangal (2013) is a popular work which portrays the Nayadis of Trivandrum district.
11. Sarah Joseph (1946-), Novelist and short story writer in Malayalam. Her novel Alahayude Penmakal (1999) deals with the marginalised class in society. Her other novels Othappu (2005) and Mattathi (2003) also discuss the suffering class.

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